

TEACHING COMPETENCE OF MUSIC, ARTS, PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND HEALTH (MAPEH) TEACHERS

Joey Ann C. Mañgila ¹, Marissa M. Damian, Ed.D. ²

¹ *Sto. Niño Academy of Bamban, Inc, Bamban, Tarlac, Philippines*

² *Institute of Graduate and Professional Studies, Lyceum–Northwestern University, Dagupan City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the level of competence of Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) teachers in School Year 2024-2025 using a quantitative-descriptive research design. The study focused on competence in subject matter mastery, content to be taught, instructional strategies, assessment, professional practice, classroom management, and facilities and equipment, as well as the seriousness of problems encountered in teaching MAPEH. The respondents of the study were MAPEH teachers in selected elementary schools in Tarlac Province, and the data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The study used weighted mean to describe the level of competence and seriousness of problems. The findings of the study revealed that the teachers were very competent in subject matter mastery, content, professional practice, and classroom management, but moderately competent in instructional strategies, assessment, and facilities and equipment. The highly serious problems were inadequate instructional materials and equipment, while the very serious problems were the lack of time to cover a large amount of content and the inability to address the needs of different learners. The overall results show that there are strengths in content knowledge and management but some weaknesses in teaching, evaluation, and resource support. A teacher enhancement program was recommended based on the findings.

Keywords: *MAPEH Teachers, Teacher Competence, Instructional Strategies, Assessment Practices, Teacher Enhancement Program*

INTRODUCTION

Quality education is first and foremost a function of instruction. For education to attain and sustain its quality, it should be coupled with the best preparation for excellent instruction. It is emphasized that to be an excellent high school teacher, one should both have full command of the subject and full knowledge of the teaching-learning process. The teacher, therefore, should not only have mastery of the subject matter, but also an in-depth understanding of the mind set and standards of students within the class.

The quality of education received by children depends on the intelligence, knowledge and professional skills of their teachers. This in turn depends on the selection of the highest-achieving candidates and high quality inspirational pre-service, support in induction and continuing professional in-service education. In summary, there are many issues and concerns in teacher education but little practical research has been done to identify good practice.

According to Loranas, et. al. (2024), teachers are the most crucial factors in improving the learning progress of learners. The learning facilities, school curriculum, school management and government policy are also considered to be important factors in determining their academic performance. However, above all, the quality of teachers becomes priorities of improvement because a teacher is the most vital component of education. In this case, teachers should be equipped with the necessary competence like pedagogic competence, personal competence, professional competence and social competence.

Teachers are the implementers of knowledge who should be competent and knowledgeable to impart the knowledge they can give to the students. Teachers must possess adequate knowledge on the objectives and standards of the curriculum, skills in teaching, interest, and appreciation of ideas about the subject. Effective teaching and learning depend on the teachers' ability to maintain the interest that would be passed to the students (Dalmacio, 2023).

With regard to the quality and competence in teaching, teachers should continually develop to attain higher education standard. Teachers should have high comprehension on subject matter and content knowledge to develop the students' achievement and to compete with the digital world. In educational practices, teachers should also be both pedagogically and socially competent to carry the daily duties as professionals and to contribute good classroom practices anchored from their knowledge, beliefs and self-efficacy (Dignath, 2021).

One of the most challenging subjects of a school teacher is Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health. Besides having four components, it focuses on the holistic development of the child. From discovering future athletes, dancers, actors and actresses, doctors and nurses, the teacher also has to discover future singers and musicians. Hence, these teachers have to perform different functions to bring out the best among the students.

According to Silvestre as cited by Martinez (2024), education is a dynamic field that continually evolves to meet the diverse needs of students in an ever-changing society. Beyond the realm of traditional academic subjects, Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) have emerged as integral components of a well-rounded education, fostering creativity, physical well-being and a comprehensive understanding of the human experience.

Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) is a curriculum implemented in Philippine schools that aims to provide holistic education to students. This curriculum is designed to develop students' creativity, health, physical fitness, and appreciation for music and the arts. MAPEH is a combination of four separate subjects, namely, Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health. Integrating these subjects is intended to develop a well-rounded, physically, mentally and emotionally healthy individual.

Music education is a vital component of a well-rounded education for school children. It offers numerous benefits to cognitive, social and emotional development. Children can develop various skills through music education, including creativity, critical thinking, communication and collaboration. One of the primary benefits of music education is its effect on cognitive development. Learning music can improve brain function, including memory, language and spatial-temporal skills (Jongko & Sagayno, 2024).

Arts education is a significant component of the MAPEH program and it encompasses various forms of artistic expressions, such as music, dance, visual arts, and theater. Arts education is essential for students' holistic development as it provides opportunities for creative expression, critical thinking and self-reflection. It also helps to develop students' cultural and social awareness and promotes their emotional and psychological well-being (Culajara, 2021).

Physical Education (PE) is a school subject that aims to develop students' physical fitness, motor skills and coordination, as well as their social skills, teamwork and sportsmanship. PE covers various physical activities such as athletics, gymnastics, dance, games, and sports. PE classes should not only focus on sports skills and physical fitness but also on developing students' social skills, self-esteem and confidence (Bartolome, 2021).

Health is essential to the MAPEH curriculum. It is an integral part of a student's education that promotes physical, mental and social wellbeing. The Department of Education (DepEd) has mandated that Health Education be taught to all elementary and high school students. DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2018 specifies that the health curriculum should engage young learners to gain the knowledge, skills and attitudes they need to make informed decisions and positively act on health-related issues and concerns (Silvestre and Itaas, 2020).

Oriarte (2023) emphasized that the Sustainable Development Goals is the global target for the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Quality Education. It is aimed to

ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. It is aimed that by 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes and to show the commitment to nondiscriminatory education outcomes.

In line with this, in the absence of well-designed development programs, teachers have been expected to learn how to improve their teaching on their own, learn from trial and error, and individually seek the required professional development. In this aspect, development program for teachers have always been essentially important.

Teachers of Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) believe that teacher quality is a key determinant of student achievement and having a strong content knowledge is crucial to effective teaching. Hence, this researcher conducts this study to determine the level of competence of MAPEH teachers in private elementary schools in Tarlac Province during the school year 2024-2025.

Research Questions

This study assessed the teachers' competence in teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) in private elementary schools in Tarlac Province during the school year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the level of competence of MAPEH teachers as perceived by the teachers themselves in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Mastery of subject matter;
 - 1.2 Content to be taught;
 - 1.3 Instructional strategies;
 - 1.4 Assessment;
 - 1.5 Professional practice;
 - 1.6 Classroom management; and
 - 1.7 Facilities and equipment?
2. What are the problems being met by the MAPEH teachers and how serious are they?
3. What enhancement program may be proposed for the MAPEH teachers to enhance their level of competence?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study assessed the level of competence of teachers of Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) during the school year 2024-2025 through the quantitative-descriptive research design.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was employed to present the level of competence of MAPEH teachers in terms of mastery of subject matter, content to be taught, instructional strategies, assessment, professional practice, classroom management, and facilities and equipment. It was also utilized to look into the problems being met by the MAPEH teachers and how serious are they

Based on the findings of the study, an enhancement program was proposed for the MAPEH teachers to enhance their level of competence.

Sources of Data

The sources of data in the study were the MAPEH teachers in selected private elementary schools in Tarlac Province who provided information to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The main data gathering tool of this study was a constructed questionnaire adapted from Gumaod, Portugues and Christy (2022) which consists of two parts to gather the information needed for the study. Part I focused on the level of competence of the MAPEH teachers in terms of mastery of subject matter, content to be taught, instructional strategies, assessment, professional practice, classroom management, and facilities and equipment. Part II looked into the problems being met by the teachers in the teaching of MAPEH.

The researcher personally distributed the questionnaires herself. After the accomplished questionnaires are retrieved, the responses of the respondents were tabulated and interpreted based on appropriate statistical tools.

Tool for Data Analysis

The following tool was used to treat the data statistically:

1. Weighted Mean

This will be employed to answer sub-problem numbers 1 and 2.
The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

- WM = Weighted Mean
- $\sum fx$ = sum of the products per column
- N = number of respondents

To interpret the data, the following references were used:

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	
		For Sub-problem No. 1	For Sub-problem No. 2
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)	Highly Serious (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)	Very Serious (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)	Not a Problem (NP)

RESULTS

Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers

This section presents the level of competence of Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) teachers as perceived by themselves in terms of mastery of subject matter, content to be taught, instructional strategies, assessment, professional practice, classroom management, and facilities and equipment to answer sub-problem number 1. The data are presented in Tables 1A to 1G.

Mastery of Subject Matter

Mastery of subject matter refers to a deep and thorough understanding of a specific field of study, encompassing not just factual knowledge but also the ability to apply that knowledge effectively and think critically about the subject. It involves a comprehensive grasp of the core concepts, principles, and methodologies within a discipline, along with the capacity to explain, analyze, and solve problems related to it. Furthermore, mastery often includes the ability to connect the subject matter to other disciplines and real-world applications.

Table 1A presents the level of competence of MAPEH teachers as perceived by themselves in terms of mastery of subject matter.

TABLE 1A
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Mastery of Subject Matter

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Presenting the subject matter tailored to the curriculum guide.	3.70	VC
• Helping learners learn the subject matter through facts and information.	3.90	VC
• Assisting learners in developing intellectual resources.	3.60	VC
• Teaching learners to cooperate with others in defining the subject matter.	4.15	VC
• Challenging learners to make sense and criticize information.	2.85	MC
• Using texts to process information accurately.	4.30	VC
• Extending beyond specific topics of the curriculum.	3.65	VC
• Letting learners explain a particular proposition deemed worth knowing.	3.20	MC
• Providing pictures in teaching.	3.55	VC
• Engaging learners' minds and hearts in learning.	3.75	VC
Overall WM	3.67	VC
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)

As presented in Table 1A, the responses in general revealed that teachers were “very competent” in teaching MAPEH in terms of mastery of the subject matter. Such was manifested with the indicators like presenting the subject matter tailored to the curriculum guide (WM=3.70); helping the learners to learn the subject matter through facts and information (WM=3.90); assisting learning in developing intellectual resources (WM=3.60); teaching learners to cooperate with others in defining the subject matter (WM=4.15); using texts to process information accurately (WM=4.30); extending beyond specific topics of the curriculum (WM=3.65); providing pictures in teaching (WM=3.55); and engaging learners’ minds and hearts in learning (WM=3.75).

The indicators “Challenging them to make sense and criticize information” and “Letting them explain a particular proposition deemed worth knowing” obtained weighted means of 2.85 and 3.20, respectively for descriptive equivalent of “moderately competent”.

The overall weighted mean was 3.67 described as “very competent”. This implies the need to provide more learning and development activities to teachers to enhance more their competence in teaching MAPEH.

Content to be Taught

Content to be taught refers to the specific subject matter, knowledge, and skills that are included in a curriculum or lesson plan. This encompasses facts, concepts, principles, and procedures that are deemed essential for students to learn within a particular subject area. Effectively teaching this content requires not only a deep understanding of the subject matter but also the ability to present it in a way that is accessible and engaging for learners. Table 1B presents the data.

TABLE 1B
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Content to be Taught

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Teaching facts, concepts, theories and principles relevant to MAPEH.	4.30	VC
• Teaching multiple content areas to a class of learners.	3.55	VC
• Including only what needs to be covered in the lesson.	4.00	VC
• Including content sources such as textbooks to access.	2.95	MC
• Remaining a prime source of delivering content if resources are not available.	3.90	VC
• Being clear on the content to be taught, what to learn, where to find it, and when it is important to use.	3.70	VC
• Not overloading learners with content.	3.65	VC
• Developing knowledge management, problem solving and decision making.	3.65	VC
• Allowing learners to use multiple resources to support the lesson.	3.75	VC
• Providing sequence on the lessons to be taught to develop focus.	4.10	VC
Overall WM	3.76	VC
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)

As presented in Table 1B, the responses in general revealed that teachers were “very competent” in teaching MAPEH in terms of content to be taught. Such was manifested with the indicators like teaching facts, concepts, theories, and principles

relevant to MAPEH (WM=4.30); teaching multiple content areas to a class of learners (WM=3.55); including only what needs to be covered in the lesson (WM=4.00); remaining a prime source of delivering content if resources are not available (WM=3.90); clearing on the content to be taught, what to learn, where to find it and when it is important to use (WM=3.70); not overloading learners with content (WM=3.65); developing knowledge management, problem solving and decision making (WM=3.65); allowing them to use multiple resources to support the lesson (WM=3.75); and providing sequence on the lessons to be taught to develop focus (WM=4.10).

The indicator “Including content sources such as textbooks to access” got a weighted mean of 2.95 and was the only one described as “moderately competent”.

The overall weighted mean was 3.76 described as “very competent”. This implies the need to assess more the content to ensure that competencies are carefully delivered.

Instructional Strategies

Instructional strategies are the methods and techniques that educators use to facilitate learning and help students acquire knowledge and skills. These strategies can be tailored to different learning styles, subject areas, and educational levels. The goal is to create engaging, effective learning experiences that go beyond rote memorization and encourage students to become independent, strategic learners. Table 1C presents the data.

TABLE 1C
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Instructional Strategies

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Making strategies about what the learner needs to learn.	1.95	SC
• Using the learning styles of the learners to fit to the strategy used.	3.00	MC
• Engaging the learners in the learning process.	2.40	SC
• Helping learners become independent learners.	3.15	MC
• Supporting learners in reaching their objectives.	3.05	MC
• Preparing learners to transition to their goal.	2.15	SC
• Training learners to be responsive to the activities.	3.30	MC
• Using experiential learning to reflect on learners' experiences to MAPEH.	3.35	MC
• Encouraging learners to participate in the instruction.	2.70	MC
• Developing group dynamics and interactive instruction like role playing and discussion.	2.85	MC
Overall WM	2.79	MC

Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)

As shown in Table 1C, the responses in general revealed that teachers were “moderately competent” in teaching MAPEH in terms of instructional strategies. Such was manifested with the indicators like using the learning styles of the learners to fit to the strategy used (WM=3.00); helping them become independent learners (WM=3.15); supporting them in reaching their objectives (WM=3.05); training them to be responsive to the activities (WM=3.30); using experiential learning to reflect on their experiences to MAPEH (WM=3.35); encouraging them to participate in the instruction (WM=2.70); and developing group dynamics and interactive instruction like role playing and discussion (WM=2.85).

The indicators “Making strategies about what the learner needs to learn”, “Engaging my learners in the learning process”, and “Preparing learners to transition to their goal” got weighted means of 1.95, 2.40 and 2.15, respectively described as “slightly competent”.

The overall weighted mean was 2.79 described as “moderately competent”. This implies the need to provide knowledge on the different instructional strategies that can be used for teaching MAPEH.

Assessment

Assessment is the process of gathering and interpreting information to make judgments or decisions about something. This could involve evaluating the quality, value, or importance of something, or assessing someone's knowledge, skills, or abilities. In education, assessment is used to understand how well students are learning and to guide improvements in teaching and learning. Table 1D presents the data.

TABLE 1D
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Assessment

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Seeing to it that the learners know and understand the assessment tools.	1.90	SC
• Supporting and assess learning through different ways.	3.25	MC
• Reporting to parents the results/grades to help them understand the learners' progress.	3.40	MC
• Recognizing achievements of the learners.	3.00	MC

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having more ways of assessing learners' progress to support learning and needs of learners. 	3.10	MC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessing including literacy, numeracy and health and well-being. 	2.25	SC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing day-to-day learning and assessment. 	1.70	SC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging learners to revisit their work if there are mistakes. 	1.85	SC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting learners to work together with others on the collaborative work. 	2.00	SC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that all have positive learning on the assessment given. 	3.00	MC
Overall WM	2.54	MC
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)

The teachers' responses as shown in Table 1D revealed that the teachers were "moderately competent" in teaching MAPEH in terms of assessment. This was manifested with the indicators like supporting and assessing learning through different ways (WM=3.25); reporting to parents the results/grades to help them understand their progress (WM=3.40); recognizing the achievements of the learners (WM=3.00); having more ways of assessing progress to support learning and needs of the learners (WM=3.10); and ensuring that all have positive on the assessment given (WM=3.00). There were five indicators with weighted means that ranged from 1.70 to 2.25 which were described as "slightly competent).

The overall weighted mean was 2.54 described as "moderately competent". This implies the need to provide teachers and learners with the right assessment appropriate to context and content.

Professional Practice

Professional practice refers to the conduct and work of someone within a specific profession, encompassing not only technical skills but also ethical behavior, decision-making, and interactions with others. It involves applying specialized knowledge and adhering to established standards, codes of conduct, and ethical principles within a particular field. Table 1E presents the data.

TABLE 1E
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Professional Practice

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Practicing reasonable and transparent behavior in teaching.	4.30	VC
• Avoiding harmful actions by embodying high ethical standards.	3.90	VC
• Communicating with learners with policies and guidelines.	3.65	VC
• Ensuring equitable services for all learners.	3.75	VC
• Resolving differences and concerns with the lesson's discrepancies.	2.85	MC
• Providing services without discrimination.	3.25	MC
• Complying with the laws in a timely and appropriate way.	4.00	VC
• Protecting confidentiality of all personal information of learners.	3.70	VC
• Engaging to inclusivity and diversity.	3.00	MC
• Engaging to be collaborative in learning.	4.25	VC
Overall WM	3.67	VC
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)

As presented in Table 1E, the teachers' responses in general revealed that they were "very competent" in teaching MAPEH in terms of professional practice. This was manifested with the indicators like practicing reasonable and transparent behavior in teaching (WM=4.30); avoiding harmful actions by embodying high ethical standards (WM=3.90); communicating with learners with policies and guidelines (WM=3.65); ensuring equitable services for all the learners (WM=3.75); complying with the laws in a timely and appropriate way (WM=4.00); protecting confidentiality of all personal information of the learners (WM=3.70); and engaging to collaborative learning (WM=4.25).

The indicators like resolving differences and concerns with the lesson's discrepancies, providing services without discrimination and engaging to inclusivity and diversity got weighted means of 2.85, 3.25 and 3.00, respectively for descriptive equivalent of "moderately competent".

The overall weighted mean was 3.67 described as “very competent”. This implies the need to provide teachers with more learning and development activities to ensure that there is an extensive understanding of how teachers should behave and act in accordance to standards.

Classroom Management

Classroom management refers to the strategies and techniques teachers use to create a positive and productive learning environment. It encompasses everything from setting clear expectations and establishing rules to maintaining discipline and fostering student engagement. Effective classroom management is crucial for both student success and teacher well-being. Table 1F presents the data.

TABLE 1F
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Classroom Management

INDICATORS	WM	DE																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and maintaining appropriate behavior management in the classroom. • Encouraging learner academic engagement. • Establishing an orderly environment in the classroom. • Emphasizing expectations for learning. • Promoting active learning and involvement. • Teaching learners to reach the learning activities. • Preventing discipline problems. • Ensuring that all learners operationalize based on the activities and lessons. • Facilitating good decision making for interventions or remedial classes. • Having consistent monitoring and evaluation of the learners’ academic progress. 	3.95 3.70 3.50 4.40 4.05 3.75 3.60 3.55 4.25 3.35	VC VC VC VC VC VC VC VC VC MC																		
Overall WM	3.81	VC																		
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Point Values</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Statistical Limits</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Descriptive Equivalent (DE)</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">4.50-5.00</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Highly Competent (HC)</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3.50-4.49</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Very Competent (VC)</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.50-3.49</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Moderately Competent (MC)</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.50-2.49</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Slightly Competent (SC)</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.00-1.49</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Not Competent (NC)</td> </tr> </table>			Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)	4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)	3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)	2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)	1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)
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2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)																		
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)																		

As presented in Table 1F, the responses in general revealed that teachers were “very competent” in teaching MAPEH in terms of classroom management. This was manifested with indicators like creating and maintaining appropriate behavior

management in classroom (WM=33.95); encouraging student academic engagement (WM=3.70); establishing an orderly environment in the classroom (WM=3.50); emphasizing expectations for learning (WM=4.40); promoting active learning and involvement (WM=4.05); teaching them to reach the learning activities (WM=3.75); preventing discipline problems (WM=3.60); ensuring that all learners operationalize based on the activities and lesson (WM=3.55); and facilitating good decision making for interventions or remedial classes (WM=4.25).

The indicator “Having consistent monitoring and evaluation of the learners’ academic progress” with weighted mean of 3.35 described as “moderately competent”. The overall weighted mean was 3.81 for descriptive equivalent of “very competent”.

Facilities and Equipment

Facilities refer to the buildings, structures, and physical spaces designed for a specific purpose, while equipment encompasses the tools, machinery, and resources used within those facilities to perform tasks or operations. Essentially, facilities provide the environment, and equipment provides the means to operate within that environment. Table 1G presents the data.

TABLE 1G
Level of Competence of MAPEH Teachers
in Terms of Facilities and Equipment

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Taking care in using facilities and equipment in teaching MAPEH.	2.20	SC
• Only using equipment that I already know how to use.	2.70	MC
• Being alert and aware in the use of facilities in relation to the topic discussed.	3.00	MC
• Performing exercises and movement, practicing good form first.	1.85	SC
• Bringing back all equipment in place after use.	2.35	SC
• Not damaging the equipment.	2.00	SC
• Returning the equipment properly or leave the venue clean.	2.60	MC
• Practicing proper hygiene and care.	2.85	MC
• Not loitering around the venue or handing on the equipment doing nothing.	3.20	MC
• Being nice when using the facilities.	3.32	MC
Overall WM	2.61	MC
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Competent (HC)

4	3.50-4.49	Very Competent (VC)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Competent (NC)

As shown in Table 1G, the responses in general revealed that teachers were “moderately competent” in the use of the facilities and equipment. Such was manifested with the indicators like only using equipment that they already know how to use (WM=2.70); being alert and aware in the use of facilities in relation to the topic discussed (WM=3.00); returning the equipment properly or leaving the venue clean (WM=2.60); practicing proper hygiene and care (WM=2.85); not loitering around the venue or hand on the equipment doing nothing (WM=3.20); and being nice when using these facilities (WM=3.35).

The indicators like taking care in using facilities and equipment in teaching MAPEH (WM=2.20); performing exercises and movement, practicing good form first (WM=1.85); bringing back all equipment in place after use (WM=2.35); and not damaging the equipment (WM=2.00) were all described as “slightly competent”. The overall weighted mean was 2.61 for descriptive equivalent of “moderately competent”.

SUMMARY TABLE

Indicators	WM	DE
• Mastery of the subject matter	3.67	VC
• Content to be taught	3.76	VC
• Instructional strategies	2.79	MC
• Assessment	2.54	MC
• Professional practice	3.67	VC
• Classroom management	3.81	VC
• Facilities and equipment	2.61	MC
Overall WM	3.26	MC

As shown in the Summary Table, classroom management had the highest average weighted mean while assessment had the lowest average weighted mean. The overall weighted mean was 3.26 described as “moderately competent”. If MAPEH teachers are only moderately competent, it can negatively impact student learning and overall educational outcomes. While they may have a basic understanding of the subject matter, moderate competence might mean they struggle with effectively delivering lessons, adapting to diverse student needs, and fostering a positive learning environment. This could lead to students missing out on crucial skills development and a deeper appreciation for the MAPEH subjects.

Problems Being Met by MAPEH Teachers

This section presents the problems being met by the Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) teachers and how serious are they to answer sub-problem number 2. The key challenges for the teachers include resource limitations, curriculum demands, teaching competency issues, classroom management concerns, and administrative pressures.

Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) teachers face a variety of challenges, including limited resources, lack of proper training, and difficulties in classroom management and inclusion. They also struggle with time management, particularly when teaching diverse learners, and may face challenges in adapting to new teaching modalities. Table 2 presents the data.

TABLE 2
Problems Being Met by MAPEH Teachers

INDICATORS	WM	DE
• Insufficient musical instruments, arts supplies, sports equipment, and health education materials	4.60	HS
• Lack of dedicated space for Art, Music practice or physical activity	3.40	MS
• Covering a wide range of topics across Music, Arts, PE and Health within limited time	4.25	VS
• Difficulty adapting curriculum to diverse learner needs and abilities	4.45	VS
• Lack of specialized training in MAPEH subjects, particularly in areas like music performance, visual arts techniques or advanced physical education skills	4.75	HS
• Difficulty assessing learner performance in creative and kinesthetic domains	3.25	MS
• Maintaining learner engagement in varied activities across different art forms	3.10	MS
• Managing large class sizes and diverse learning styles	2.90	MS
• Difficulty communicating the importance of MAPEH education to parents	2.25	SS
• Securing parental support for extracurricular activities and practice time	2.85	MS
• Balancing MAPEH teaching with other responsibilities like grading, paperwork and reporting	2.65	MS
• Pressure to achieve standardized test scores in a subject that is often not heavily weighted	2.15	SS
Overall WM	3.38	MS

Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Serious (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Serious (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not a Problem (NP)

As presented in Table 2, “highly serious” problems being met by MAPEH teachers include insufficient musical instruments, arts supplies, sports equipment, and health education materials and lack of specialized training in MAPEH subjects, particularly in areas like music performance, visual arts techniques or advanced physical education skills with weighted means of 4.60 and 4.75, respectively.

Many schools lack a sufficient number of variety of instruments for students to learn and practice and Art classes may be hampered by a lack of basic materials like paper, paints, brushes, and other necessary tools. Physical education classes may also struggle with limited or outdated sports equipment, hindering learners’ ability to participate in various activities. Health lessons may also be compromised by a shortage of resources like posters, models or age-appropriate books,

A significant problem for MAPEH teachers is the lack of specialized training in their specific subject areas. This can lead to difficulties in effectively teaching the curriculum, managing classrooms, and adapting to diverse learning needs. Teachers who are not specialists in MAPEH may struggle with the depth and breadth of the curriculum, potentially leading to less effective instruction. The active and creative nature of MAPEH subjects can be challenging to manage, especially when teachers lack specific training in classroom management techniques for these subjects. Since teachers need to be able to adapt their lessons to cater to learners with varying abilities and learning styles, lack of specialized training can make this difficult, leading to disengagement among learners. Teachers may struggle to effectively utilize available resources, including facilities, equipment and instructional materials, if they have not received specific training on how to do so within the context of MAPEH. The lack of opportunities for targeted professional development in MAPEH can exacerbate the issue, leaving teachers feeling ill-equipped to address the unique demands of the subject.

Proposed Enhancement Program for the MAPEH Teachers

This section presents the proposed enhancement program for the Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) teachers to enhance their level of competence to answer sub-problem number 3.

An enhancement program for MAPEH typically focuses on improving learner performance, teacher development and the overall learning environment. This involves

implementing strategies like project-based learning, extracurricular activities and professional development for teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn

1. Generally, the MAPEH teachers in public elementary schools are moderately competent as perceived by themselves which means they struggle with effectively delivering lessons, adapting to diverse student needs, and fostering a positive learning.
2. Problems being met by MAPEH teachers include insufficient musical instruments, arts supplies, sports equipment, and health education materials and lack of specialized training in MAPEH subjects, particularly in areas like Music performance, visual arts techniques or advanced physical education skills.
3. The proposed enhancement program focused on improving learner performance, teacher development and the overall learning environment.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The proposed enhancement program should be considered for implementation to enhance the MAPEH teachers' level of competence.
2. School heads, master teachers and MAPEH teachers should continue to work together to sustain the implementation and support system of the MAPEH program.
3. School administrators should support any initiatives that foster collaboration among teachers and recognize their contributions to create an environment that encourages open dialogue.
4. School administrators should continuously strengthen their monitoring and professional development activities for the teachers' professional advancement.
5. Future researches are encouraged to conduct a similar study on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

Rationale

Findings of the study indicated that the MAPEH teachers are “very competent” in terms of mastery of the subject matter, content to be taught, professional practice and classroom management; and “moderately competent” in terms of instructional strategies, assessment, and facilities and equipment.

	identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to the program
Specific examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAPEH Club – Establish a club that offers various activities related to Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health, catering to different learner interests • Talent Show – Organize a talent show to provide a platform for learners to showcase their talents in singing, dancing and other performing arts. • Art Exhibit – Hold an art exhibition to display learners’ creative works in various art forms. • Sports Competition – Conduct regular sports competitions to encourage participation and improve learners’ physical fitness and athletic skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to the ethical standards of research. Permission to conduct the research was sought from the relevant authorities in the concerned schools. The participation of the respondents in the research was voluntary, and they were required to give their consent before the data was collected. The respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and the data collected was for academic and research purposes only. There was no form of coercion, deception, or harm involved in the conduct of the research.

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REFERENCES

- Bartolome, L. L. (2021). Implementation of physical education program of selected state universities in CALABARZON region, Philippines in relation to students' skills development. *International Journal of Research Publications*.
<https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP100751420211884>
- Culajara, C. J. (2021). Competency level of MAPEH teachers in teaching performing arts on K to 12 curriculum in secondary public schools. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. <https://doi.org/10.52877/instabright.003.02.0036%20>
- Dalmacio, C. P. H. (2023). Assessment of instructional difficulties of music, arts, physical education and health teachers: Basis for developing a capability program. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.
<https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=22763>
- Dignath, C. (2021). For unto every one that hath shall be given: teachers' competence profiles regarding the promotion of self-regulated learning moderate the effectiveness of short-term teacher training. *Metacognition Learning* 16, 555–594 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-021-09271-x>.
- Gumaod, J. D. F., Portugues, S. M., & Donato, R. A. C. (2022). Level of competence among MAPEH teachers in the Division of Surigao del Norte, Dinagat Islands and Camarines Sur. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijsms-v5i4p134>
- Jongko, R. A., & Sagayno, R. C. (2024). Music, arts, physical education and health (MAPEH) learning objectives' level of attainment and utilization of learning resources. *British Journal of Teacher Education and Pedagogy*.
<https://doi.org/10.32996/bjtep.2024.3.1.3>
- Loranas, V. S., Serviñas, L., & Eslabon, L. P. (2024). Implementation, support system and difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability and Excellence*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13207696>
- Martinez, E. C. (2024). Management support to MAPEH program implementation and teachers' competency: Basis of a proposed action plan. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.
<https://scimatic.org/storage/journals/11/pdfs/3620.pdf>
- Oriarte, R. C. (2023). Instructional competencies of teachers and their performance in the execution of task. *International Journal of Business, Law and Education*.
<https://doi.org/10.56442/ijble.v4i1.102>

Silvestre, M. D. P., & Itaas, E. C. (2020). Lived experiences of teachers teaching music, arts, physical education and health (MAPEH): Implications to graduate education. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*.
https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT20DEC053.pdf?utm_source